

Research Paper

Evaluations of antioxidant and antibacterial activities of plant *Albizia lebbek* (L.) Benth.

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation evaluates the antioxidant and antibacterial properties of methanolic extracts of the leaves, seeds, and stem bark of *Albizia lebbek* (L.) Benth., a well-known medicinal tree that is commonly used in traditional Indian medicine. Methanol was used for Soxhlet extraction of plant materials, and ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) and DPPH free radical scavenging evaluations were used to assess the antioxidant capacity. Zone of inhibition and activity index measurements were used to assess antibacterial efficacy against specific Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains. The DPPH assay displayed dose-dependent free radical scavenging activity, with seed extract exhibiting comparatively lower IC₅₀ values (47.120 mg/mL) than leaves (48.987 mg/mL) and stem bark (50.373 mg/mL), though all were less effective than the standard ascorbic acid. According to FRAP analysis, seed extracts had the highest reducing power (IC₂₀ = 10.136 mg/mL), which suggests that they have a better ability to donate electrons. According to antibacterial studies, methanolic extracts, especially those from stem bark, significantly inhibited the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, with Gram-positive bacteria being more susceptible. Overall, the results confirm the ethnomedicinal significance of *Albizia lebbek* and demonstrate its potential as a promising source of natural antioxidant and antibacterial agents for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical industries.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional medicines are still used in the basic healthcare systems of poor nations. In order to treat a variety of illnesses, natural products are

now preferred over contemporary synthetic medications. In order to provide rural residents with effective healthcare support, it is now increasingly crucial to maximise the benefits of the traditional medicine system (Shafiq *et al.*, 2023;

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Raks *et al.*, 2018). Ethno medical validation combined with phytochemical and biological activity screening is an effective method for finding new drugs made from medicinal plants (Sharma *et al.*, 2022). Bioactive chemicals with potential therapeutic benefits are largely derived from medicinal plants. The secondary metabolites of plants are the source of several phytochemicals that may be utilised to create novel medications. Secondary metabolites are a vast range of compounds from various metabolite families. These can be largely activated in response to stresses. The existence of secondary metabolites may be responsible for the antioxidant activity, and the distribution of secondary metabolites, which may vary among plant organs, may account for the variation in the IC₅₀ value. The polarity of the solvents and, thus, the extractability of the antioxidative chemicals may be the cause of variations in the antioxidant activity of the extracts (Petrus *et al.*, 2012). *Albizia lebbbeck (L.)* Benth. is a deciduous, medium-length tree. The traditional therapeutic usage of *Albizia lebbbeck* is supported by the relationship between biological activity and phytochemical makeup. Its potential use in pharmaceutical and nutraceutical compositions is suggested by the antioxidant and antibacterial qualities observed. The plant *A. lebbbeck (L.)* Benth. has several therapeutic applications and is employed in the Indian medical system for both wood and medicinal purposes. The leaves are valuable and high in protein, and many different cultures use them as part of their diet. Rich in tannins, saponins, and other organic and inorganic materials, the bark is utilised for a variety of purposes, including the tannin industry and colours (Gull *et al.*, 2024). The flavonoids isookanin, luteolin, geraldone, and catechin were isolated from the bark. Additionally, many triterpenoids and saponin compounds have been isolated from stem bark (Bajpai *et al.*, 2024). Numerous phytochemicals, including phytosterols

tocopherols, eight phenolic acids, mostly cinnamic acid, and eight flavonoids, including chrysoeriol, hesperidin, and quercetin, were found in the acetone extract of *A. lebbbeck* stem bark (Ibrahim and Abdul-Hafeez, 2023).

Methodology

The various parts of the plant, such as the leaves, seeds, and stem bark of *Albizia lebbbeck (L.)* Benth, were gathered from the Jaipur district. The various plant parts—leaves, seeds, and stem bark—were cleaned with tap water, let too dry at room temperature in the shade, crushed with an electronic grinder to a fine powder, and then placed in airtight containers. The experimental materials, each weighing 100 g, were soxhlet extracted after the 24 to 36 hours using methanol solvents.

Determination of Antioxidant activity

DPPH assay

The free radical scavenging activities of the methanol extract of different plant parts were evaluated by using the modified method of (Blois, 1958). 1.0 ml each of the different concentrations of extracts or standard (Ascorbic acid) was added to 1ml of 0.3 mM DPPH (in methanol). The mixture was vortexed, and after 30 minutes of incubation in a dark chamber, the absorbance at 517 nm was measured against a DPPH control that contained just methanol instead of the extract.

FRAP assay

In this test, methanol and chloroform extracts of various plant sections were used to measure the FRAP activity. Plant extracts were allowed to react with the FRAP solution for 30 min in the dark condition. Readings of the coloured product (ferrous tripyridyltriazine complex) were taken at 593 nm.

Identification of antimicrobial activity

The sequential extracts were raised to final concentration 10 mg/ml in dimethyl sulfoxide (10% sterile DMSO), before use to screened for antimicrobial activity. The media-containing petriplates was utilised for antimicrobial screening once they have dried. After being injected into nutrient broth, the bacterial cultures were cultured at 37°C for 24 hours. By measuring the width of the inhibitory zone surrounding the extract-filled well, the antibacterial properties of the extracts were assessed following incubation. The zone of inhibition, which is measured in millimetres, is a clearly defined region that is produced when plant

extracts with antimicrobial properties prevent bacterial growth in the media around the wells.

Activity Index = Inhibition zone produced by extract/Inhibition zone produced by standard

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

By using digital spectrophotometer, DPPH scavenging demonstrated in dose-dependent inhibition (2–10 mg/mL), with IC₅₀ values suggesting potency: ascorbic acid (33.834 mg/ml) compared to seeds (47.120 mg/ml), leaves (48.987 mg/ml), and stem bark (50.373 mg/ml).

Table-1 DPPH scavenging activity and IC₅₀ value of different plant parts at various concentrations

	Conc. (mg/ml)					IC ₅₀ mg/ml
	2 mg/ml	4 mg/ml	6 mg/ml	8 mg/ml	10 mg/ml	
Leaves extract	3.753	4.912	6.457	8.554	10.430	48.987
Seeds extract	7.119	9.216	10.486	12.583	14.625	47.120
Stem bark extract	0.331	4.470	5.740	7.009	9.272	50.373
Ascorbic acid	35.541	38.852	40.728	41.832	43.046	33.834

Fig.-1 Percent radical scavenging activity of different plant parts at various concentrations

Fig.-2 IC₅₀ value of different plant parts

The ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) technique relies on antioxidants in an acidic media reducing a ferrioxal analogue, the Fe³⁺ complex of tripyridyltriazine Fe(TPTZ)³⁺, to the highly blue-

colored Fe²⁺ complex Fe(TPTZ)²⁺. The use of various solvents may be the cause of the notable variations in the FRAP activity of the extracts.

Fig.-3 Percent FRAP activity of different plant parts at various concentrations

FRAP results suggested reducing power of extracts. In comparison to leaves (58.135 mg/mL) and stem bark (34.925 mg/mL), seeds had the highest FRAP lowering capability (IC₅₀ 10.136 mg/mL). Seed extract exhibited the most

significant reducing ability and the lowest IC₅₀ value. The activity of leaf and stem bark extracts was modest. The high protein and lipid content of seeds, which may stabilise free radicals, is correlated with their considerable FRAP action.

Fig.-4 IC₅₀ value of different plant parts

Table-2 FRAP activity and IC₅₀ value of different plant parts at various concentrations

	Conc. (mg/ml)					IC ₅₀ mg/ml
	2 mg/ml	4 mg/ml	6 mg/ml	8 mg/ml	10 mg/ml	
Leaves extract	35.514	37.584	36.724	36.569	37.226	58.135
Seeds extract	37.799	41.359	42.483	41.920	43.531	10.136
Stem bark extract	8.100	10.403	10.172	11.700	13.592	34.925
Ascorbic acid	48.460	52.920	56.218	59.390	63.095	1.316

Previous phytochemical screening of these plants revealed that the extracts had antimicrobial properties and were positive for a variety of primary and secondary compounds, including proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, tannins, and alkaloids extracted by various solvents (Ahad *et al.*, 2021). *A. lebeck* extract was biologically active as an antibacterial agent against *B. subtilis* and *S. marcescens* and had moderate activity against *A. johnsonii* and *A. tumefaciens*, while *E. carotovora* and *E. coli* were the least affected (Ibrahim and Abdul-Hafeez, 2023). The antibacterial activity of methanolic extracts was often stronger than that of aqueous extracts. The antimicrobial potential of methanolic extracts of

Albizia lebeck was evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Overall, stem bark performed exceptionally well against *S. aureus* (12.5 mm), *E. coli* (14 mm), *B. subtilis* (11.5 mm), and *P. aeruginosa* (10.5 mm). Higher zones of inhibition were observed in stem bark, especially against *B. subtilis* and *E. coli*. Bacteria *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* showed the highest activity index values. Leaves/seeds were comparable but weaker (in seeds *E. coli* 12.5 mm). Mild effectiveness is indicated by activity indices (AI range 0.3-0.6). All bacteria were consistently inhibited by leaf extracts. The bactericidal activity of seed extracts was moderate. Gram-positive (*B.*

subtilis, *S. aureus*) When plant extracts disrupt peptidoglycan over lipopolysaccharide, their sensitivity surpasses that of Gram-negative.

Antibacterial activity of methanol extract was better than aqueous extract, but *P.aeruginosa* was found to be most resistant (Suganya *et al.*, 2011) bacterial pathogens of humans. The antibacterial

activity of the methanol extract was greater than that of the other two solvents. According to Kumawat *et al.* (2012), the methanolic extract of stems has strong efficacy against *B. subtilis* and *S. typhi*. According to Sharma *et al.* (2013), Gram-negative bacteria were more susceptible than Gram-positive ones.

Table-3 Comparisons of Zone of Inhibition and Activity index for different bacterial strains.

Microorganism		Plant part used					
		Leaf		Seed		Stem bark	
		Replica-I	Replica-II	Replica-I	Replica-II	Replica-I	Replica-II
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Zone of Inhibition (mm)	11	12	10	11	13	12
	Activity index	0.354839	0.521739	0.416667	0.611111	0.419355	0.521739
<i>E. coli</i>	Zone of Inhibition (mm)	13	15	11	14	14	14
	Activity index	0.371429	0.46875	0.366667	0.636364	0.583333	0.451613
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Zone of Inhibition (mm)	11	15	14	13	13	10
	Activity index	0.314286	0.625	0.451613	0.619048	0.565217	0.333333
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Zone of Inhibition (mm)	12	9	11	11	10	11
	Activity index	0.333333	0.45	0.366667	0.52381	0.47619	0.52381

Fig.-5 Compare Average Activity index for different bacterial strains.

CONCLUSIONS

The current study supports the traditional medical usage of *Albizia lebbek* (L.) Benth. by showing that it has significant antioxidant and antibacterial

properties. In the FRAP test, methanolic extracts of leaves, seeds, and stem bark demonstrated dose-dependent ferric reducing power and DPPH radical scavenging activity, with seed extracts displaying the most antioxidant efficiency. Stem bark extracts were very efficient against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Bacillus subtilis*, according to antibacterial screening. The higher tendency of Gram-positive bacteria indicates that phytochemicals in *A. lebbeck* may especially disrupt peptidoglycan-rich cell walls. To enable its sensible application in current therapies, additional studies need to focus on the isolation, characterisation, and mechanistic assessment of individual bioactive chemicals as well as in vivo validation.

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